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BALKAN HYDROGEN CLUSTER

D 5.4

Networking with other projects and initiatives

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Deliverable abstract

The present document D5.4 "Networking with other projects and initiatives" is a Delivery of Work Package 5 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation.

This deliverable intends illustrates the communalities and the networking of HYPOP project with other Initiatives and Projects (EU, national, regional, etc.) in the sectors of:

- hydrogen technologies
- energy
- climates,
- carbon free,
- green economy
- public engagement,
- etc.

The above synergies are characterized by each HYPOP's Partner and relative country.

Keywords

Hydrogen, green technologies, energy, decarbonisation, citizens, project communalities.

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Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodородen Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement

Executive Summary

This document describes the synergies of the HYPOP project with other projects (EU, national, regional, etc.) which deal with green economy issues both from the point of view of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies and similar technologies which in any case pertain to the achievement of the "carbon free" objective in the next decades. Public opinion and stakeholder engagement initiatives have also been included.

Each HYPOP's Partner have specific collaborations/relations with other projects to get in contact with in their own country and outside. Many of these contacts come out from previous activities performed within WP1, WP2. Relative WP's deliverables integrate the present report with other information and details on projects and hydrogen players' network.

The principal criteria and actions of projects/initiatives identification are below summarized:

- analysis of the different approaches in EU state members with the main focus on the HYPOP partners Countries (WP1)
- info by EU NCPs (energies, climates in particular) regarding related and similar activities (WP1, WP2)
- public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technology (WP1)
- public opinion regarding H2 implementation in EU countries in terms of technology understanding and acceptance (WP1)
- networking and collaboration with other EU-funded (but also regional and national) projects and initiatives
- attend conferences in the hydrogen sector to present results, guidelines and toolboxes developed through HYPOP (WP5)
- Communication and Dissemination dedicated Plan (social media, workshop, etc.) (WP5)
- National and European Hydrogen Technologies roadmaps (energy, transportation, automotive, etc.) (WP1).

The following paragraphs illustrates the above activities, synergies and collaborations, but also future plan of synergy and networking implementation.

1 Introduction

1.1. Context and background

Project HYPOP - HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance, Grant Agreement nr 101111933 is a project supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, and co-funded by the European Union.

Project HYPOP's Overall Objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a web platform, and social media, collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

To reach the overall goals of the project, 2 different target groups will be targeted, engaged and involved directly in dedicated activities:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyze the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies.

The development of Hydrogen technologies and their integration into the market energy can represent an important opportunity to face the challenge of climate neutrality and the energy crisis that Europe, its economy and its citizens are currently living through.

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

This Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation aims at outlining an adequate and impactful approach towards awareness raising and outreach, supporting thus strongly the engagement of relevant stakeholders in the project activity and preparing the ground for the use of its results.

1.2. Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP

HYPOP will strive to achieve the following specific objectives:

- Understanding public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies
- Identification of the main individual-level determinants of public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technologies
- Enhancing involvement of citizens in the implementation of solutions contributing to the transition to hydrogen and fuel cells
- Understanding the pathways to influence public opinion by analysis of the current depiction of hydrogen technologies in broadcasts, newspapers, and social media, and from this developing a public information strategy
- Assessment of the specific role of the socio-economic and environmental impacts of hydrogen technologies
- Clear guidance on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorisations for installing hydrogen technologies
- Engagement on Hydrogen Technologies' implementation
- Identifying the safety approaches and the safety barriers in a range of different Countries, in order to create a map of the main requirements (certification) for installing hydrogen technologies and facilities
- Identifying the attitudes of the different countries towards social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of the hydrogen technologies

Through its different operational activities, HYPOP will aim to achieve the objectives mentioned above, whilst the transversal work of “impact maximisation”, which includes communication and dissemination, will act in support: the aim being to **leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them into the project activities (in line with the stakeholder engagement strategy of the project) and the exploitation of results.**

Below the main project outcomes and expected impacts:

- Outcomes:
 - Reach a deeper comprehension of the public opinion on hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the social awareness, trust and reduction of the social distance to the hydrogen topic
 - Improvement of the understanding of the hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the scientific community and stakeholders' awareness of the public opinion on hydrogen topic, limits and possible drivers into the acceptance process
- Impacts:
 - Socio-cultural (increase the knowledge and acceptance)
 - Environmental/Climatic (hydrogen is a valid energy carrier used to produce clean energy with environment benefits)
 - Scientific (create more efficient technologies to integrate into the market)

- Political (improvement and acceptance of the energy strategy proposed to address the challenges of reaching climate neutrality and mitigating the energy crisis in Europe)
- Economic (long-term benefits in terms of infrastructure, and energy supply at small and large scale).

2 HYPOP Networking and Synergies

2.1 H2 Projects with HYPOP Communalities and Synergies

Present chapter illustrates projects, initiatives and other networks detected by each HYPOP's partner during this first year of project. Many of the listed projects refer to EU, national, regional or local level initiatives from energy/hydrogen topic to social awareness initiatives.

In some cases direct contacts have been established, in others cases projects have been just identified indirectly by using public events, stakeholders meetings, blog, articles. Synergy and collaborations will start in the second year of project.

The identified projects have been listed reporting the following information:

- Partner of contact;
- Topics;
- Short description;
- HYPOP Communalities.

2.1.1 APRE

Project Name:

MARINEWIND (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02, 25 July 2022)

Topics:

Environmental engineering
Energy and fuels
Renewable energy
Social science
Climate and mobility

Short description:

MARINEWIND is a 36 months coordination and support action that will identify bottlenecks and potential opportunities to strengthen floating offshore wind's technology FOWT role in delivering innovative solutions to system integration and will consider how best to integrate such a system by exploring the market, policy and regulations issues, social, financial and techno-economic optimal solutions, and provision for storage and flexibility recommendations. The MARINEWIND methodology is based on the analysis of the MARINEWIND Labs, that are social, environmental, technological and financial pilot studies based upon a multi-faceted data collection and analysis on barriers and enablers related to: a) policy measures (WP1); b) societal engagement and environmental impact (WP2); c) financial solutions, techno-economic implications and commercialization of FOWT (WP3). The MARINEWIND Labs are located in five countries: Portugal and UK (actual applications of FOWT) and Greece, Spain and Italy (planned applications of FOWT). These Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWT are still at various stages of planning or

implementation. The MARINEWIND Labs will involve the Quintuple Helix stakeholders (industry, academia, public authorities, civil society and green innovation). The threefold analysis will be conveyed into the MARINEWIND web based Geographical Information System (webGIS) which will provide specifically tailored information on FOWT to the various stakeholders on the basis of their category, geographical location and their goals and policy recommendations on how to have more informed RES policy and how to increase societal acceptance (WP4). The Replicability Plan will support the transfer of knowledge. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (WP5) will assure widespread outreach of the projects' results and outcomes and to reach its impacts.

Communalities with HYPOP:

Carbon free
Green and circular economy
Social awareness

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Project Name:

ALFA (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02, 1 November 2022)

Topics:

Biogas
Energy
Sustainable industries and agriculture

Short description:

Europe could double the biogas and biomethane production by 2030 by utilising the massive amounts of animal waste available. However, despite the technological maturity and commercial availability of relevant technologies, this promising potential is still largely untapped. In this context, ALFA supports at least 50 livestock farmers in 6 EU counties (IT, DK, DE, BE, SK, EL, ES) to overcome existing barriers and viably take up biogas systems. We start by establishing regional Hubs that analyse the local framework conditions and livestock value chains, and help engage local stakeholders in co-designing our approach. Then, we enhance selected livestock farmers' business and technical capacity by providing them with a series of demand-driven financial, business, and technical support services and organising dedicated capacity-building seminars. In parallel, we develop an Engagement Platform hosting tools that facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange among industry actors and provide credible estimations of each farm's biogas potential, prospect profits, environmental and social impacts. Also, we improve the societal acceptance of biogas facilities amongst citizens by 25% (or above) through well-tailored awareness-raising campaigns. At the same time, we trigger the development of an enabling environment for the market uptake of biogas by formulating relevant policy recommendations and widely disseminating them to more than 60 policymakers. Finally, a monitoring and evaluation framework evaluates the performance and impact of all the above, providing us with the intel required to catalyse mutual learning across regions and contribute to creating a guide for

replicating our results. Therefore, we expect a power output of 30 MWel by our supported cases / projects, leading to an increased share of renewable energy in the final energy consumption in the target countries and ultimately, saving 270,000tn CO2 and 330,000tn CO2-eq from manure management per year.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*New energies
Carbon free
Innovative industries
Energy generation*

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Project Name:

SUPERSHINE (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-02, 1 November 2022)

Topics:

*European Green Deal
Energy efficiency
Sustainable lifestyles*

Short description:

The objectives and impacts of the SUPERSHINE project will assist and support the European Commission to implement the European Green Deal. Particular attention will be paid to the renovation of social housing, to help households who struggle to pay their energy bills. In addition, SUPERSHINE will also contribute to the decrease of energy poverty. The SUPERSHINE lighthouse districts will be characterised by energy efficient buildings, low carbon mobility, smart grids, efficient water and waste management, all underpinned by responsive technologies that optimise resources while promoting wellbeing and sustainable lifestyles. More specifically, SUPERSHINE will adopt an integrated strategy with these key principles: a) 'Energy efficiency first'; b) Affordability; c) Decarbonisation and integration of renewables; d) Life-cycle thinking and circularity; e) High health and environmental standards by promoting sustainable energy behaviours; f) Tackling the twin challenges of the green and digital transitions together; g) Respect for aesthetics and architectural quality. The main areas of intervention are: a) Strengthening information and incentives for public and private owners and tenants to undertake renovations while improving community participation or inspiring new patterns of citizen behaviour; b) Ensuring adequate and well-targeted funding by supporting innovative bottom up financial solutions such as Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and Green Public Procurement (GPP) and collaborating with innovative local Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); c) Promoting comprehensive and integrated renovation interventions; d) Making the construction ecosystem fit to deliver sustainable renovation, based on circular solutions, use and reuse of sustainable materials, and the integration of nature-based solutions while reducing whole life-cycle carbon emissions.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Green transition
Decarbonization
Citizen green behaviour
Carbon emission reduction*

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Project Name:

THOT2 (HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-1, 26 January 2023)

Topics:

*Energy and fuels
Hydrogen technologies
Environmental engineering*

Short description:

How maximize hydrogen (H₂) blending potential in natural gas (NG) networks, supporting European energy system decarbonisation? The answer lies in the need of a systemic, multi-disciplinary approach to make NG infrastructure resilient to the challenges of tomorrow. Industrial and research players' competences are required. In this framework, THOTH2 consortium focuses on energy measurement value chain and instruments' ability to accurately measure physical parameters of H₂NG mixtures with increasing H₂ percentages, up to 100%. Including gas TSOs, DSOs, metrological and research institutes and academia, THOTH2 consortium has all competences and skills to reach the goals of i) define standards to evaluate the metrological performances of measuring devices at different H₂ blending rates (up to 100%), ii) verify safety and durability of the same devices, and iii) suggest future needs to overcome the observed barriers and limitations. SNAM competences in managing NG assets are essential for the coordination and synergic integration of the 14 partners, recognized as experts in NG and H₂ industry (GRTGAZ, GAZ-SYSTEM, Enagás, INRETE), metrology (CESAME, INRIM, METAS), H₂ blending technologies and measuring devices design, engineering, and R&D activities (UNIBO, INIG, FBK, ENEA, CSIRO). The communication and dissemination strategy by GERG will give visibility to project's results, including contributions to Mission Innovation 2.0 and EURAMET projects. THOTH2 vision will lead to an acceleration towards H₂ economy, contributing to REPowerEU and NextGeneration EU objectives. The project impact potential includes the establishment of a R&D Hub center, including THOTH2 partners and Advisory Board members, to translate into valuable results achieved by the project, aiming to i) the development/update of international standards, ii) foster innovation in the field of H₂NG blending measuring devices, and iii) supporting H₂ value chain development leveraging on the EU gas infrastructure

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Green hydrogen
Decarbonization
Natural gas blending
Carbon emission reduction*

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Project Name:

FLEX4H2 (HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-04-04, 3 December 2022)

Topics:

*Low-emission combustion
Environmental engineering
Hydrogen technologies*

Short description:

The project aims at moving technological frontiers for low-emission combustion of hydrogen to fuel modern gas turbines at high firing temperatures and pressures, beyond the latest state-of-the-art. This will be achieved whilst maintaining high engine performance, efficiency, fuel and load flexibility, without diluents. At the same time, all emission targets set by the Clean Hydrogen JU Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) will be met.

The idea is based on a proprietary combustion technology, designated constant pressure sequential combustion (CPSC) already deployed into the GT36 H-class engine (760 MW in combined cycle). The CPSC concept, based on a unique longitudinally staged combustion system, yields the best fuel flexibility and has the greatest potential to achieve the project target of demonstrating stable and clean combustor operation with concentrations of hydrogen admixed with natural gas, up to 100%, at firing temperatures typical of modern H-Class engines. The new, improved combustor design will be fully retrofittable to existing gas turbines, thereby providing opportunities for refurbishing existing assets.

The primary objective is to demonstrate the CPSC technology in engine relevant environment (TRL6) in three steps (70, 90 and 100 vol% H₂). In this pursuit, a subset of specific performance data (KPIs) will be met within the project timeline and with the planned resources and allocated budget.

The project uses state-of-the-art computational tools, analytical modelling, and diagnostic techniques to investigate static and dynamic flame stabilisation. Testing is performed at world-class laboratories in test campaigns at reduced scale and in full size (at atmospheric and pressurised conditions).

In preparation for commercialisation, the project will also develop a roadmap towards

deployment of the developed system into operation and demonstration into a power plant environment quantifying the valuable contributions to the EU Green Deal.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Low emission
Decarbonization
Fuel flexibility
Energy and mobility*

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Project Name:

TH2ICINO (HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-06-02, 30 June 2023)

Topics:

*Hydrogen Valley
Eco technologies
Green industries*

Short description:

TH2ICINO (Towards H2ydrogen Integrated eEconomies In NOrthern Italy) supports the deployment of micro hydrogen economies for the EU by developing and demonstrating a full ecosystem integrated by 6 replicable use cases linked to the steps of the hydrogen value chain. The results will validate a Master Planning Tool (MPT), which replicability will be then tested.

The demonstration of the hydrogen valley will work on the four pillars of the hydrogen value chain: (i) hydrogen production, (ii) hydrogen storage, (iii) hydrogen distribution, and (iv) hydrogen consumption and will send the initial status of TH2ICINO in order to enable replication and expansion. A first stage will include modelling, simulation and scenarization, from electrolysis plant to end-user in order to evaluate different scenarios and optimize them taking into consideration the technological constraints. Once the optimal cases are defined, an implementation phase will bring to real-life the innovative concept of the ecosystem tangible results to feed the MPT.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Hydrogen production
Hydrogen distribution
Hydrogen citizen awareness and acceptance*

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Project Name:

PROMETEO (H2020-JTI-FCH-2020-1, 9 December 2020)

Topics:

*Green hydrogen production
Energy storage
Sustainability*

Short description:

PROMETEO aims at producing green hydrogen from renewable heat & power sources by high temperature electrolysis in areas of low electricity prices associated to photovoltaic or wind.

Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE) is a highly efficient technology to convert heat & power into hydrogen from water usually validated in steady-state operation. However, the heat for the steam generation may not be available for the operation of the SOE when inexpensive power is offered (e.g. off-grid peak, photovoltaics or wind). Thus, the challenge is to optimize the coupling of the SOE with two intermittent sources: non-programmable renewable electricity and high-temperature solar heat from Concentrating Solar (CS) systems with Thermal Energy Storage (TES) to supply solar heat when power is made available.

In PROMETEO a fully integrated optimized system will be developed, where the SOE combined with the TES and ancillary components will efficiently convert intermittent heat & power sources to hydrogen. The design will satisfy different criteria: end-users' needs, sustainability aspects, regulatory & safety concerns, scale-up and engineering issues.

The players of the value-chain will play key roles in the partnership created around the project: from developers and research organizations, to the electrolyzer supplier, system integrator/engineering and end-users.

A fully-equipped modular prototype with at least 25 kWe SOE (about 15 kg/day hydrogen production) and TES (for 24 hours operation) will be designed, built, connected to representative external power/heat sources and validated in real context (TRL 5). Particular attention will be given to partial load operation, transients and hot stand-by periods.

Industrial end-users will lead to techno-economic & sustainability studies to apply the technology upscaled (up to 100 MW) in on-grid & off-grid scenarios for different end-uses: utility for grid balancing, power-to-gas, and hydrogen as feedstock for the fertilizer & chemical industry.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Energies production, conversion and storage
Fuel cells
Hydrogen Technologies awareness and acceptance
Hydrogen Valleys*

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Project Name:

AMON (HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-04-02, 9 December 2022)

Topics:

*Hydrogen technologies
Fuel cells
Power generation*

Short description:

AMON project aims at developing a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell. High temperature electrolyzers have demonstrated in several activities the capacity to outreach high performances in lab scale prototypes and validation tests. The project will deal with the design of the basic components of the system including the fuel cell, the ammonia cracker, the ammonia burner and an anode gas recirculation, the engineering of the whole Balance of Plants, and the validation of the compliance with ammonia use for all the specific parts and components. For the development of the solid oxide fuel cell, a G8X cell from SOLIDpower will be utilized, first validated in a laboratory at the level of single cells, for electrochemical properties, degradation and post mortem analysis, at the level of single repeating units for the validation of interconnects and sealing components, and at the level of stacks and stack modules.

An overall Ammonia fuel cell system will be engineered and manufactured to be tested in a relevant environment in a port area. The final system will be in the size of 8 kW stack module, with an ammonia cracker and a heat management system. It will aim at a overall electrical efficiency in the range of 70%.

AMON will be supported alongside the engineering by horizontal strategic support on critical and open issues involving use of ammonia with fuel cells, such as safety assessment, on techno-economic analysis, on modelling at a multiscale and multiphysic levels, to consolidate, confirm and direct the engineering of the technology. Despite the small pilot demonstration scale, AMON will propose a scaled engineering for a system suitable to be applied in end uses such as ports, interports, maritime environment, besides autonomous power systems.

AMON will promote the use of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier, to enhance the flexibility of the energy system.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Energy efficiency
Decarbonisation*

*Autonomous power systems
New technologies and components
Cost energies reduction
Decarbonization*

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Project Name:

FORGING (HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01, 1 October 2022)

Topics:

*Innovative technologies
Industry 5.0
Green technologies*

Short description:

Technological breakthroughs empowered by enabling technologies hold a transformation potential that can be funneled to address industrial and societal grand challenges, like greening and digitalisation. To exploit this transformative potential, the innovation journey that leads new emerging technologies to their market-uptake shall embed since its early value-sensitive considerations, such as environmental and societal implications. With FORGING we propose a new methodology based on a value-sensitive innovation journey that breaks linear innovation trajectories to stimulate new technological visions and pathways attentive to the environment and society, and human-centred in alignment with Industry 5.0. technological frameworks. The value-sensitive innovation journey will be deployed in three phases: the technological uncovering with tech experts from academia and industry to detect early signals of emerging technologies; the societal confluence exploring the desirability and societal impact, and implications of novel technologies; the full-fledged co-creation opening to the broader community to develop concrete use cases for tech uptake. We will develop 6 Technological Pathways to transfer ideas and help industry navigate through issues related to the absorption and deployment of the use cases. FORGING methodology will be implemented by catalysing stakeholders' community with 600 active members, from academia to industry, to CSS, to policy makers and to the broader society. We aim to organise 24 co-creation sessions, consultations with 20 policy bodies, 6 scenario workshops and Tech. and Innovation campaigns to drive tech. adoption. The FORGING Playbook and Toolbox will gather a set of facilitation guidance and materials for exploration, reflection, co-creation and evaluation of emerging technologies. These assets, jointly with the FORGING community, will sustain FORGING as a new flagship initiative on emerging enabling technologies.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*European Green Deal
European Industrial Strategy
Emerging technologies (hydrogen, fuel cells, etc.)*

*Sustainable society
Citizen awareness and acceptance*

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In collaboration with ENVI, a number of NCPs – National Contact Points on energy, climate, transportation topics in a number of different were contacted in order to receive support for the activities of the project. Focusing on the first year’s tasks, the NCPs were asked to either provide or direct the team towards experts who could provide the following specific information:

- *We are interested to understand what strategic documents have been produced at national, regional and local level in your countries concerning green/renewable hydrogen and its technologies;*
- *Are there any public (citizens and/or authorities) perception surveys on acceptance of hydrogen and its technologies (cars, buses, trains, storage systems, hydrogen refueling stations...)? Are there any public entities (ministries....) or private entities directly involved in this topic in your country?*
- *Are there any videos of hydrogen technologies/projects that could be shared on the future HYPOP web platform (aforementioned) by stakeholders?*
- *Which is the legislative framework in your country related to installation of hydrogen technologies (or for other similar fuels in case of legislative gap)? We are interested in those safety and permitting requirements asked to build a Hydrogen Refueling Station, an hydrogen production plant or to install other hydrogen technologies like storage systems, compressors...*
- *Which are the main public entity at national, regional or local level involved in the evaluation and approval of hydrogen projects for safety and permitting?*
- *We are also interested to understand which are the certification requirements (technical standards, EU directives...) for hydrogen technologies market uptake in your country, especially for those more innovative ones (like demonstrators and prototypes) that struggle more to achieve the CE marking;*
- *Are there any relevant hydrogen projects (H2 valleys or H2 projects funded at national and regional level) that you could provide us? Do you have any contacts from the partners involved in those projects?*

Some EU Countries involved:

- *Estonia*
- *Greece*
- *Rep. Ceca*
- *Rep. Slovakia*
- *Slovenia*
- *Latvia*

- *Romania*
- *Croatia*
- *Cyprus*
- *Hungary*
- *Lithuania*
- *Malta*

2.1.2 ENVI

ENVI's networking activities focused mainly on interactions with stakeholders active in public and private hydrogen projects to gather information for the tasks within WP1 and WP2 on analysis of strategies and of safety, permitting and certification requirements. These activities contributed substantially both to raise awareness of the project objectives and to the drafting of deliverables D1.1 “State-of-the-art analysis of EU-Countries H2 strategies”, D2.1 “Report on safety requirements”, D2.2 “Report on permitting requirements”, D2.3 “Report on certification requirements: certification instruments to facilitate the acceptance by safety and permitting authorities”.

Projects:

An initial list of projects of interest was created, including those with the following characteristics:

- a) Topic covering safety, certification, standardisation, interaction with institutional stakeholders (first responders, public authorities)
- b) Demonstrating innovative technologies
- c) Installation of electrolysers or refuelling stations and Hydrogen valleys/territorial projects, including those so called under the Italian Recovery Plan.

a) Safety, standardisation

HYRESPONDER. <https://hyresponder.eu/>, coordinated by Ulster university

H2020, January 2020 to May 2023

Objective: The specific objectives of the project include **the development of clear and updated operational, virtual reality, and educational training for trainers of responders to reflect the state-of-the-art in hydrogen safety.** Using feedback from the network on national specificities, educational training materials will be adapted where required to reflect regional peculiarities. The materials for responders will be translated and made available in 8 languages via an e-Platform. National Training Clusters will be developed to consolidate links between the hydrogen safety and responder communities and to support the delivery of workshops at a national level.

➔ Produced educational content for first responders that could help to reduce risk perception

e-SHyIPS - Ecosystemic knowledge in Standards for Hydrogen Implementation on Passenger Ship

H2020, January 2021 – December 2024

The current approach to hydrogen vessel design lacks a clear and dedicated normative framework and early-stage management of risks. The EU-funded e-SHyIPS project will connect hydrogen and maritime sectors with international-level experts. They will conduct a regulatory framework review and assess experimental data on ship design, safety systems, material and components, and bunkering procedures. The project will formulate a pre-standardisation plan for an updated IGF Code for hydrogen-fuel passenger ships and a roadmap to promote the hydrogen economy in the maritime ecosystem.

More specifically:

E-SHIPS will identify and ensure the correct management of risks in all aspects related to design and operation of passenger ships.

The project has **five objectives**:

- Generate new and missing knowledge to define a standardized database and a data gathering methodology on the arrangement and installation of hydrogen-based fuels systems for propulsion and auxiliary purposes.
- Provide unique experimental data for the definitions of mandatory criteria for the arrangement and installation of machinery, equipment and systems for vessels operating with hydrogen-based fuels to minimize the risk to the ship, its crew, passengers and the environment.
- Propose a pre-standardization plan for IGF code update for the hydrogen-based fuels passenger ships international regulation.
- Provide a roadmap for the adoption of hydrogen-based fuels on passenger ships in EU maritime sector, to boost the hydrogen economy.
- Develop CFD models and tools for ship design and safety assessment, by exploiting the potentialities of Complex System Simulation SWs and HPC, in synergy with the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking.

➔ Useful repository for the standardization framework (D1.3 e D1.4), also for the approach identified

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b) Innovative technologies

HyCARE - Hydrogen CARRIER for Renewable Energy Storage, coordinated by University of Turin

H2020, January 2019- July 2023

The HyCARE hydrogen storage tank is based on a solid-state carrier, using metal hydride that will be part of a renewable energy plant exploiting the use of H₂ as energy vector for stationary energy storage. The energy produced by renewable sources is used to produce H₂ from water through an electrolyser. The gas is then stored in the HyCARE tank using a solid-state carrier. A heat storage system based on phase change materials collects the heat produced by the renewable plant, the electrolyser and from the metal hydrides, during H₂ absorption.

REMOTE - Remote area Energy supply with Multiple Options for integrated hydrogen-based Technologies, coordinated by Politecnico di Torino

H2020, January 2018- June 2023

REMOTE demonstrates technical and economic feasibility of two fuel cells-based H₂ energy storage solutions (integrated P2P system; non-integrated P2G+G2P system), deployed in 4 DEMOs, based on renewables, in isolated micro-grid or off grid remote areas.

It also undertook an analysis of the economic and regulatory framework of the technological demonstrators; and provided general indications concerning the engineering and permitting procedures of H₂-based energy storage systems.

TULIPS - DementsTrating lower pollUting soLutions for sustalnable airPorts across Europe Horizon Europe, Jan 2022- Dec 2025

The EU-funded TULIPS project will accelerate the implementation of innovative and sustainable technologies targeting reduced greenhouse gas emissions at airports. The project will roll out 17 demonstrations of green airport technological, non-technological and social innovations at Amsterdam Airport Schiphol and at the Oslo, Turin and Larnaca airports. TULIPS will measure and quantify the benefits of these technologies and concepts and forecast their impact on EU climate goals. The project will consider economic, geographical and political scenarios to deliver a robust roadmap presenting the way of implementation from international hubs to the regional level.

H2Ports - Implementing Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Technologies in Ports

H2020, Jan 2019- Dec 2024

The project will evaluate and demonstrate new fuel cell technologies to increase the energy efficiency and safety of port terminals. The prototypes selected are a reach stacker for handling cargo containers, a terminal tug master for roll-on/roll-off operations and a mobile hydrogen supply station.

RESHIP - Redefine energy Efficiency solutions for hydrogen powered SHIPs in marine and inland waterway

Horizon Europe, Sept 2022 – August 2025

RESHIP project will develop a comprehensive solution towards zero-emission waterborne transport. Focusing on the development of new devices and onboard technologies, the project aims to save energy and reduce the demands of hydrogen storage on ships. A multidisciplinary consortium will develop, demonstrate and validate technologies at technical, environmental, cost effective, safety and regulatory levels.

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sMArt Green Ports as Integrated Efficient multimodal hubs

Horizon Europe, Oct 2021- Sept 2026

The EU-funded MAGPIE project will embark on 12 pilot activities in three key areas: alternative energy sources; smart technologies applied to power operations; and river and rail connections with the hinterland. The ports of Rotterdam (Netherlands) and Sines (Portugal), as well as Haropa Port (France) and the DeltaPort association (Germany) are supporting the project. MAGPIE will combine the accelerated introduction of green energy carriers with logistics optimisation in ports through automation and autonomous operations. The project will demonstrate technical, operational and procedural energy supply solutions to stimulate green, smart and integrated multimodal transport, and guarantee their implementation through the European Green Ports of the Future Master Plan.

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FuelSOME - Multifuel SOFC system with Maritime Energy vectors

Horizon Europe, Sept 2022-August 2026

The FuelSOME project focuses on establishing the technological feasibility of a flexible, scalable, and multi-fuel capable energy generation system based on Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) technology specially catered for long-distance maritime shipping. This system will be able to operate on Ammonia, Methanol and Hydrogen and their mixtures for which short and long-term sustainable supply pathways will be explored. Finally, on a broader level, an in-depth and detailed investigation on the environmental, social, and economic benefits of developing such a system for the European industry, the maritime sector and the citizens will be carried out.

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SWITCH - SMART WAYS FOR IN-SITU TOTALLY INTEGRATED AND CONTINUOUS MULTISOURCE GENERATION OF HYDROGEN

H2020, Jan 2020- March 2024

SWITCH project aims to develop fuel cell technology that will provide green and secured production of hydrogen, heat and power. The core of the system will comprise three elements: a reversible solid oxide module based on anode-supported electrolytes; a fuel processing unit

that can manage steam generation and methane-reforming reactions at high efficiency; and a purification unit to guarantee highly pure hydrogen in compliance with the main automotive standards. The goal is to demonstrate a 25-kilowatt SOFC system operating in an industrial environment for 5 000 hours.

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MultHyFuel - MULTI-FUEL HYDROGEN REFUELLING STATIONS (HRS): A CO-CREATION STUDY AND EXPERIMENTATION TO OVERCOME TECHNICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE BARRIERS

H2020, Jan 2021- Dec 2023

EU-funded MultHyFuel will contribute to effective deployment of hydrogen by developing a common strategy for implementing hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) in multi-fuel contexts. The project will generate best practice guidance on the basis of data and evidence derived from practical experimentation, engage key stakeholders (policy makers, public authorities, standardisation bodies)

The project developed a deliverable on Permitting requirements and Risk assessment methodologies for HRS in the EU

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PROMETEO - Hydrogen PROduction by MEans of solar heat and power in high TEmperture Solid Oxide Electrolysers

H2020, Jan 2021 – June 2024

PROMETEO project will optimise the coupling of solid oxide electrolysis (the hydrogen generator) with intermittent renewable heat and power from solar energy with the help of a thermal energy management system (TEMS). The PROMETEO prototype will consider three industrial applications as end-users.

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GRASSHOPPER - GRid ASsiSting modular HydrOgen Pem Power plant

H2020, January 2018- March 2022

The GRASSHOPPER project aims to create a next-generation MW-size Fuel Cell Power Plant unit (FCPP), which is more cost-effective and flexible in power output, accomplishing an estimated CAPEX below 1500 EUR/kWe at a yearly production rate of 25 MWe. This unit will be operated continuously for 8 months in industrially-relevant environment for engaging grid support modulation as part of an established on-site Demand Side Management (DSM) programme in Nouryon facilities in Delfzijl (Netherlands)

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CH2P- Cogeneration of Hydrogen and Power using solid oxide based system fed by methane rich gas

H2020, Feb 2017 – April 2022

CH2P aims at building a transition technology for early infrastructure deployment. It uses widely available carbon-lean natural gas (NG) or bio-methane to produce hydrogen and power with Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) technology. Similar to a combined heat and power system, the high quality heat from the fuel cell is used to generate hydrogen. CH2P realised two systems, one with hydrogen generation capacity of 20 kg/day, for components validation, and another at 40 kg/day for infield testing. The CH2P project targets the emerging market of hydrogen refueling stations (HRS). It will exploit synergies between the Energy and the Transport sectors to provide a high-performance system prototype for HRS.

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GrInHy2.0 - Green Industrial Hydrogen via steam electrolysis

H2020, Jan 2019- Dec 2022

A demonstration plant will showcase the hydrogen production via steam electrolysis using waste heat from an iron-and-steel factory. GrInHy2.0 marks the first implementation of a high-temperature electrolyser with a nominal power input of 720 kilowatt in an industrial environment. The hydrogen will be used for annealing processes as a substitute for hydrogen produced from natural gas. The system was launched at the Salzgitter Flachstahl GmbH steelworks.

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THyGA - Testing Hydrogen admixture for Gas Applications

H2020, Jan 2020- March 2023

Researchers will test around 100 residential gas appliances in various hydrogen concentration scenarios, and provide a generic protocol that can be adapted for virtually any appliance. Ultimately, they will make recommendations along the gas value chain for appliance design, manufacture and certification.

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c) Valleys or similar territorial based projects

H2iseO Hydrogen Valley https://www.fnmgroup.it/h2iseo_hydrogen_valley/

An Italian hydrogen-based industrial value chain for a sustainable mobility system in Val Camonica, backed by the Lombardia regional government with RRF financial resources, and that will provide hydrogen along the Brescia-Iseo-Edolo railway line, gateway to the Milan-Cortina 2026 Winter Olympic Games and currently non-electrified.

The first phase of the project involves the arrival of the first 6 hydrogen-powered electric trains, which will be built by Alstom and delivered by 2024. By first half 2025, a first hydrogen production plant will also be built at the Iseo station.

➔ **the project coordinator, the railway operator FNM, already assigned the tenders of all the production and distribution facilities in Brescia, Iseo and Edolo.**

1. the production and distribution of hydrogen in **Brescia** was tendered on 31 of July 2023 to Renova Red Spa and railway operator Consorzio Stabile Appaltitalia.

2. for the production and distribution plant in **Edolo** a single tender for technical design and construction of both plants, and their maintenance has been assigned on 6 of July to Consorzio Innova Società Cooperativa and BTP Infrastrutture Spa;

3. For **Iseo**, the production and the distribution plant have different tenders. The tender for the distribution plant was assigned to Sirma Spa. Instead, the tender for the production plant has been assigned on 14 of September to two other companies, F.Ili Trentini e Hysytech, belonging to the same holding of Sirma spa.

➔ firefighters have already expressed their favourable opinion about the executive project which will arise in FNM Group location

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A subproject called **GreenHyseo Project** has been funded under InnovFund-SSC-2020 on the CCS technology for the Iseo hydrogen production plant that uses steam reforming technologies. Specifically, the project plans not only to produce hydrogen to fuel the trains and bus fleets but to make the process greener by capturing the CO2 thus obtaining a significant GHG emission avoidance.

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H2 Valcamonica project

-Project coordinator: A2A SPA

- Project beneficiaries: SNAM S.P.A, FNM SPA

Innovation Programme, Jan 2022- Dec 2024

This project aims to create the first integrated hydrogen value chain in Italy. It has been funded under the Innovation programme and it will provide green hydrogen for mobility application and energy intensive industries in the area of Brescia, Northern Italy. The technologies involved are an electrolyser for hydrogen production, a storage and compression system (to store the hydrogen at the production site), and a storage system functional to the distribution point (to allow refuelling of trains at the station). It should be operational by 2026

The energy needed to produce hydrogen will be supplied by renewable energy produced by the waste-to-energy power plant in Brescia. Some 43% of the energy produced by the plant is

certified as green and it will be used to produce green hydrogen. The site will produce a forecasted 830 tonnes per year of hydrogen, based on 43 870 MWh of electricity and 16 600 m³ of water.

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NORTH ADRIATIC HYDROGEN VALLEY

Horizon Europe funds - Large scale hydrogen valley, September 2023 – August 2029

It will be built between **Friuli Venezia Giulia region (Italy)** and Slovenia and Croatia. The project will activate 17 testbed applications in their related ecosystems, clustered in 3 main pillars - hard to abate, energy and transport sectors. Four fuel cell applications in the energy and transport sectors will be demonstrated. Replicability will also be ensured for the whole NAHV model, with the uptake of at least 5 additional hydrogen valleys in Europe, particularly in Central and South Eastern Europe.

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LIFEALPS Zero Emission Services for a Decarbonised Alpine Economy

LIFE Strategic Integrated Project, 2019-2027

The project (LIFEalps builds on the successful pilot projects of the past and takes the decisive step towards a regional roll-out of electric mobility. LIFEalps is one of the first major European projects to promote zero-emission mobility in a technology-neutral manner: both hydrogen refuelling stations and charging stations for battery-electric vehicles will be installed and put into operation. However, as to avoid the chicken and egg problem, fleets of emission-free vehicles of various categories are also being brought onto the streets at the same time. These infrastructures and emission-free vehicles will then serve as the basis for applications and services that make zero-emission mobility tangible. Infrastructures and vehicles fleets are the main pillars. Planning phase for HRS are ongoing in the South Tirol region. EURAC is undertaking data monitoring and social perception studies on electric and FC buses.

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BIG HIT

H2020, May 2016 – April 2022

BIG HIT will create a hydrogen territory in the Orkney Islands of Scotland by implementing a fully integrated model of hydrogen production, storage, transportation and utilisation for heat, power and mobility.

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Direct contacts:

ENVI contacted many stakeholders including italian contacts amongst the partners of the projects identified. One to one meetings were set up to explain the project and its aim and to obtain information through a structured interview similar to the questionnaire sent to the

NCPs throughout Europe. Amongst the projects partners or coordinators contacted, research organisations such as ENEA, Politecnico di Torino, FBK, the Istituto per le Innovazioni Tecnologiche Bolzano, industry representatives such as Tecnodelta, Hysytech, A2A, business support organisations such as RINA were interviewed. Furthermore, significant stakeholders of the hydrogen economy development in Italy were also interviewed to gather experiences with safety, permitting and certification, understand if any public perception survey/analysis had been undertaken and if they wanted to provide examples of hydrogen installations to be published on the HYPOP website.

Very interesting discussions, for instance, were held with the coordinator of the more advanced of the Italian Hydrogen Valleys on their approach to the permitting authorities. Other hydrogen valleys were still behind in the planning phase and had not yet tackled the issue.

On the other hand, the area of Sud Tyrol could bring their experience on the public perception of hydrogen buses, which was shared with the WP1 leader. Overall, territorial-based projects, however, did not appear to have addressed the issue of public perception with many foreseeing installations of production facilities in industrial areas.

With respect to other stakeholders, ENVI networked with ANIMA Idrogeno, a subgroup of the Italian Metal Industry Association based in Lombardy with about 90 companies involved. HYPOP project was presented to the associates during a group meeting.

A strong support has been given by the Italian Hydrogen Association H2IT, who is currently involved in supporting the regulatory bodies in the drafting of Italian legislation on hydrogen production, storage and distribution. Aspects linked to the public acceptance are also on the agenda of the association, which groups around 140 stakeholders (industry, research centers) of the hydrogen value chain.

2.1.3 IMI

Project Name:

HY4RES: Hybrid solutions for Renewable Energy Systems (Interreg Atlantic Area, 2023-2026)

Topics:

*Blue and green environment
Renewable energy
Sustainable energy sources*

Short description:

HY4RES is working on creating new technology that uses renewable energy sources, like wind and solar power, along with smart data systems to help communities in the Atlantic Area become more energy-efficient. The main challenge they are tackling is how to use more renewable energy in different regions by coming up with smart ways to store and manage it.

The project will focus on developing advanced systems that combine different renewable energy sources, like wind, solar, and hydropower, and store that energy for when it's needed. They also plan to create affordable and eco-friendly power systems. Another important part of the project is to build intelligent software that uses sensors, big data analysis, and artificial intelligence to better manage and predict how different renewable energy sources work together in a hybrid system.

The goal is to help local communities and industries, like agriculture, aquaculture, and ports, to benefit from using more renewable energy and becoming more self-sufficient. This way, HY4RES can contribute to reducing their carbon footprint and move towards using more sustainable energy sources.

Communalities with HYPOP:

HYPOP and HY4RES both aim to advance sustainable energy solutions in the Atlantic Area:

- *Both focus on integrating renewable energy sources into communities.*
- *They aim to enhance energy efficiency through innovative technologies.*
- *Both projects seek to benefit local communities and industries.*

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Project Name:

HYDEA: Boosting the hydrogen transition in the Atlantic Area ports (Interreg Atlantic Area, 2023-2026)

Topics:

*Blue and green environment
Green hydrogen technologies
Renewable energy
Decarbonization*

Short description:

HYDEA is about making green hydrogen technologies a big part of how ports work in the Atlantic Area. Green hydrogen is a clean energy source, and the project wants to use it along with other renewable energies in ports to make things more energy-efficient and reduce carbon emissions. To make this happen, the project plans to develop tools and approaches that will be like building blocks for changing how ports use energy. They want to address the challenges and problems that come with using hydrogen in ports. Here's how:

- *Helping everyone understand, making sure that everyone involved knows more about hydrogen and how to use it;*

- *Trying out new technologies, supporting research and development by testing out different technologies in real situations, like pilot projects along the hydrogen supply chain;*
- *Figuring out how to make it work as a business, looking at different ways to make using hydrogen in ports a practical and profitable choice.*
- *Creating plans for ports and policymakers, helping ports and policymakers in the Atlantic Area to play a big role in using hydrogen as a clean energy source.*

The main goal of HYDEA is to make ports in the Atlantic Area more energy-efficient and use clean energy like hydrogen, contributing to a cleaner and more sustainable way of running things.

Communalities with HYPOP:

Both HYPOP and HYDEA focus on promoting hydrogen technologies for sustainability. They aim to:

- *Increase public awareness.*
- *Test and implement hydrogen technologies.*
- *Address economic viability.*
- *Engage stakeholders for collaboration.*

Project Name:

PLAST4H2: Plastic circularity through an efficient detection, collection, and valorization into Hydrogen and value-added products (Interreg Atlantic Area, 2023-2026)

Topics:

*Blue and green environment
Plastic circularity
Sustainability
Waste management*

Short description:

PLAST4H2 is on a mission to tackle plastic pollution in the Atlantic Area by focusing on circularity and sustainability. Partners want to turn plastic waste into valuable products, such as hydrogen, and encourage people to make eco-friendly lifestyle choices. The project brings together a group of people and organizations using a four-part approach.

In the first part, they're figuring out the extent of ocean pollution, creating tools to detect it, mapping how litter moves in the water, and testing an advanced system to collect plastic using a special boat. The second part involves showing off new and creative ways to turn plastic into useful things like hydrogen, energy, and eco-friendly plastics. The third part is all

about making sure these processes are sustainable and spreading awareness about the benefits. They plan to demonstrate their solutions through four pilot projects, reaching thousands of people.

PLAST4H2 wants to make its technologies available to everyone involved, including decision-makers. They're determined to promote green practices in the Atlantic region and play a part in protecting our oceans and building a sustainable future for everyone.

Communalities with HYPOP:

Both HYPOP and PLAST4H2 reflect a commitment to integrating sustainable technologies into daily life and boosting public and stakeholder support. They focus on:

- *Enhancing public awareness and trust in green technologies.*
- *Engaging communities and stakeholders to support the adoption of these technologies.*
- *Demonstrating sustainable practices through pilot projects to showcase the practical benefits and encourage broader adoption.*
- *Developing assessment tools—HYPOP uses indicators for social impact, while PLAST4H2 creates tools to manage and measure pollution and recycling efficacy.*

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Project Name:

SAtComm: Sustainable Atlantic Communities (Interreg Atlantic Area, 2023-2026)

Topics:

*Blue and green environment
Clean energy
Smart energy
Energy communities*

Short description:

The SAtComm project is about giving Energy Communities the tools they need to be in control of their energy and actively contribute to making our energy systems cleaner. New rules from the European Union are making individual energy users more central in the shift towards cleaner energy. However, each country in the EU is adopting these rules in its own way, which is making it challenging for Energy Communities to have a significant impact on this transition.

SAtComm plans to look into the rules in the four Atlantic Area regions, create and use technologies that work for everyone, and make sure they're sustainable. This way, all sorts of energy users, from industries to homes, will have the power to do things like trade energy directly with each other, manage their energy use wisely, shift when they use electricity, and

store energy in batteries. The project will test these technologies in rural and coastal areas in all four regions, and the lessons learned will be shared so that other Energy Communities can use them as a guide to adopting similar smart energy concepts.

Communalities with HYPOP:

HYPOP and the SAtComm project are committed to sustainable energy solutions and stakeholder engagement. They both:

- *Empower stakeholders—HYPOP with hydrogen technology users, SAtComm with Energy Communities.*
- *Respond to policies—each adapting strategies to fit regional or national frameworks.*
- *Promote sustainability through innovative energy solutions and practices.*
- *Implement demonstration projects to validate their technologies and encourage wider adoption.*
- *Facilitate knowledge sharing to spread successful practices and lessons learned.*

2.1.4 IME

Project Name:

eGHOST (FCH-04-3-2020, Grant No. 101007166, Jan 2021 – May 2024)

Topics:

*Ecodesign
Fuel cells and hydrogen
Sustainable-by-design products*

Short description:

Ecodesign is a strategic factor for the fulfilment of the EU's commitment to a climate-neutral and circular economy in 2050. The EU-funded eGHOST project aspires to become a reference for the transition to a climate-neutral and circular economy in 2050 by ensuring an optimised design and use of hydrogen systems. eGHOST aims at supporting the fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) sector with a framework for the sustainable eco-(re)design of mature and emerging products and the promotion of FCH technologies as an environmentally-friendly and socially-responsible investment.

Commonalities with HYPOP:

*Social life cycle assessment of hydrogen-related systems
Socially-responsible design of hydrogen-related products*

Project Name:

SH2E (FCH-04-5-2020, Grant No. 101007163, Jan 2021 – Jun 2024)

Topics:

*Fuel cells and hydrogen
Life cycle assessment
Life cycle costing
Life cycle sustainability assessment
Social life cycle assessment*

Short description:

Hydrogen is an essential element in the transition to a low-carbon society. Besides technological advances in the field, life-cycle assessment studies are crucial for evaluating the suitability of hydrogen technologies and supporting decision-making.

These studies should rely on well-defined guidelines. The goal of the EU-funded SH2E project is to draw up specific guidelines for environmental, economic, social and sustainability life-cycle assessment and benchmarking of fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) systems.

Commonalities with HYPOP:

*Decision-making support
Guidelines for social life cycle assessment of hydrogen-related systems*

Project Name:

HyPEF (HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2023-05-01, Grant No. 101137575, Jan 2024 – Dec 2026)

Topics:

*Fuel cells and hydrogen
Life cycle assessment
Product environmental footprint*

Short description:

Fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) systems are increasingly considered in energy and climate policies, roadmaps and plans all over the world. In order to avoid past criticalities, such as those leading to a climate emergency situation, sustainability criteria are being progressively implemented in these initiatives, e.g. by promoting low-carbon renewable hydrogen in Europe. In this regard, science-based criteria and procedures are required to guarantee the environmental suitability of FCH products, reporting their life-cycle environmental profile

according to the principles of transparency, traceability, reproducibility, and consistency for comparability. While these principles are aligned with those of the general methodological guidance for Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) studies, further specification is required to effectively implement them when addressing FCH products.

Hence, the HyPEF project aspires to support and promote the establishment of an environmentally-responsible hydrogen economy by developing and testing the first Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs) specific to FCH products, while paving the way for subsequent related initiatives in the FCH sector. HyPEF is conceptualised as the natural step forward in methodological specification towards policy- and market-relevant life-cycle environmental assessment and benchmarking of FCH products. The interdisciplinary approach behind HyPEF leads to crucial advancements regarding (i) the first development and application of well-accepted PEFCRs tailored to three pre-selected FCH product categories (electrolysers for hydrogen production, tanks for hydrogen storage, and fuel cells for hydrogen stationary use), (ii) increased high-quality data availability for consistent environmental assessment and benchmarking of FCH products, and (iii) first PEF-oriented policy recommendations towards official qualification of an FCH product as an environmentally-responsible investment.

Commonalities with HYPOP:

Life-cycle approach to hydrogen-related systems

2.1.5 CNH2

The projects related with HYPOP are:

Project Name:

HYACINTH (FCH-JU-2013-1, September 2014 – May 2017)

Topics:

- Environmental engineering*
- Renewable energy*
- Fuel cell technologies*
- Social science*

Short description:

The objective of this project is to achieve a greater understanding of the social acceptance of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies and applications at European level, to develop a tool to facilitate the product development and market introduction being better aimed to the target audience, giving better response to the expectations and deduced the risks or barriers to their acceptance.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Carbon free
Green and circular economy
Public understanding
Social acceptance
Communication and management tools*

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Project Name:

GREEN HYSLAND (H2020-JTI-FCH-2020-1, January 2021 – December 2025)

Topics:

*Environmental engineering
Energy and fuels
Renewable energy
Social science
Climate and mobility
Hydrogen valleys*

Short description:

The project brings together all core elements of the H2 value chain i.e. production, distribution infrastructure and end-use of green hydrogen across mobility, heat and power. The overall approach of GREEN HYSLAND is based on the integration of 6 deployment sites in the island of Mallorca, including 7.5MW of electrolysis capacity connected to local PV plants and 6 FCH end-user applications, namely buses and cars, 2 CHP applications at commercial buildings, electricity supply at the port and injection of H2 into the local gas grid. The intention is to facilitate full integration and operational interconnectivity of all these sites.

The project will also deliver the deployment of infrastructure (i.e. dedicated H2 pipeline, distribution via road trailers and a HRS) for distributing H2 across the island and integrating green H2 supply with local end-users. The scalability and EU replicability of this integrated H2 ecosystem will be showcased via a long-term roadmap towards 2050, together with full replication studies.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Carbon free
Green and circular economy
Social awareness
Hydrogen valleys*

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Project Name:

H2PORTS (H2020-JTI-FCH-2018-1 1 January 2019 - 31 December 2024)

Topics:

*Environmental engineering
Renewable energy
Port Equipment
Fuel Cells
Energy Efficiency*

Short description:

The H2Ports project will demonstrate and validate at the Port of Valencia in real port operations two innovative solutions based on FC technologies and a hydrogen mobile supply station specifically designed for the project. A Reach Stacker to be tested in MSC Terminal Valencia and a Yard Tractor to be tested in Valencia Terminal Europa (part of Grimaldi's group) have been selected as those specially fitted to the use of Fuel Cells in port facilities. The project will run the equipment on a daily basis during two years of real operational activities and will analyse ways of improving the energy efficiency, performance and safety of operations with Fuel Cells port equipment. The project will also take into account transversal issues such as the human factor, regulation, the future roll out of the technology on a fully commercial basis and the raise of awareness of the potential of hydrogen adoption as an alternative fuel in port equipment.

H2Ports aims to boost the transition of the European port industry towards an effective low-carbon/zero-emission and safe operative model, piloting, evaluating and demonstrating new Fuel Cell technologies oriented to increase energy efficiency, decarbonisation and safety of port terminals. The pilots to be tested in the project will be the first experiences of the use of hydrogen technologies in port handling equipment in Europe.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Carbon free
Green and circular economy
Demonstrative projects
End users*

2.1.6 RIGP

Project Name:

H2GLOBAL: European Green Hydrogen Cluster Alliance for Internationalisation (COS-CLUSINT-2020-3-01-1 September 2021 – February 2024)

Topics:

*Hydrogen Clusters partnerships
Business network collaboration*

Short description:

The project aims to contribute to position Europe as the world's technological and industrial leader in the green hydrogen economy. To achieve this ambition, H2GLOBAL is building a strong collaboration network among European leading energy Clusters to configure a “European Strategic Cluster Partnership - Going International” focused on Cluster cooperation and internationalization tailored to supporting and promoting hydrogen-related businesses, technologies and services.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen partnerships
European Industrial Strategy*

EU countries involve:

- *Spain*
- *France*
- *Portugal*
- *Italy*
- *Poland*

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Project Name:

GreenSkills4H2 - The European Hydrogen Skills Alliance (ERASMUS-EDU-2021-PI-ALL-INNO July 2022 – June 2026)

Topics:

*Hydrogen value chain
Technic and academic training
Technic and academic qualification*

Short description:

The Green Skills for Hydrogen Project (GreenSkillsforH2) is contributing to the development of a skilled workforce in Europe for the emerging hydrogen economy by addressing the skills gap and providing training to boost the industry.

The Green Skills for Hydrogen project has collaborated closely with hydrogen stakeholders across the European Union to identify the occupational profiles in high demand in the sector and analyse the required level of “hydrogen knowledge” of these profiles. This study has enabled us to outline what we call the European Hydrogen Skills Strategy.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
European Hydrogen Skills Strategy*

EU countries involve:

- Greece
- Austria
- France
- Belgium
- Nederland
- Denmark
- Spain
- Romania
- Bulgaria
- Germany
- Ireland
- Italy
- Poland
- Estonia

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Project Name:

H2Excellence:Fuel Cells and Green Hydrogen Centers of Vocational Excellence towards affordable, secure, and sustainable energy for Europe (ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PEX-COVE June 2023 – June 2027)

Topics:

*Hydrogen value chain
Technic and academic training
Technic and academic qualification*

Short description:

The H2Excellence project will establish the H2Excellence Platform of Vocational Excellence in the field of fuel cells and green hydrogen technologies which will create and implement lifelong learning opportunities including online learning platform and develop national and international curricula and training programmes. The project will establish several local clusters, i.e., Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs), fully integrated into the innovation, skills, and job ecosystem in green hydrogen and fuel cell technologies in six Erasmus+ countries (Italy, Spain, Finland, Portugal, Poland, and France) and two support/associated CoVEs in the other two Erasmus+ countries (France and Poland). The project will continuously expand networks both domestically and internationally throughout the several European regions and countries in order for people to exchange knowledge and profit from one another. The project will also be internationalized in North America via cooperation and partnership for VET opportunities and exchange programmes between the EU and Canada.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
European Industrial Strategy*

EU countries involve:

- *Italy*
- *Spain*
- *Finland*
- *Portugal*
- *Poland*
- *France*

Project Name:

*Hyperion - Hydrogen uptake in European regions
(Interreg Smarter Europe April 2024 - June 2028)*

Topics:

*Good practices for uptake of H2 solutions
Improved hydrogen policies
Creation of regional ecosystems*

Short description:

HYPERION supports European regions in the complex process of taking up advanced Hydrogen (H2) solutions in various areas of their economic systems, as a move towards a smart and sustainable economic transition.

H2 can support affordable decarbonisation of industry and can be produced by renewable energies. Public policy supports H2 integration in hard-to-abate and energy-intensive sectors and transport. A further policy focus in recent times are hydrogen valleys.

The challenge for Europe regions is to identify and implement most effective, efficient and place-based means of boosting the huge potential of H2. H2 currently makes up less than 2% of EU's energy mix and is still largely produced from fossil fuels (2022).

A large, diverse and experienced group of partners, all committed to the roll out of advanced H2 solutions in their territories, participates in HYPERION to face this challenge through interregional learning.

Their overall aim is to build regional ecosystems for a sustainable industrial transition based on innovative H2 solutions, in synergy with S3/S4 strategies.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
Building regional hydrogen strategies
Regional policy improvements*

EU countries involve:

- *Belgium*
- *Italy*
- *Romania*
- *Poland*
- *Spain*
- *Finland*
- *Norway*
- *Denmark*

2.1.7 CLUSTER TWEED

Project Name:

GreenSKHy (Interreg North-West Europe January 2024)

Topics:

*Hydrogen value chain
Technic and academic training
Technic and academic qualification*

Short description:

The aim of our project is to promote the development of the clean hydrogen sector by reducing the obstacles to the European recognition of skills and related systems through joint action plans and by promoting careers that can contribute to the energy transition through new practical training schemes. This ambition involves networking the actors in charge of skills and certifications, developing and testing specific training and acculturation modules, and implementing campaigns to promote the hydrogen sector and its opportunities. By bringing together within the consortium companies, public authorities as well as the main actors of initial and continuous training, the project should therefore support the development of a key sector for the energy transition by ensuring the empowerment of a large audience.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
European Industrial Strategy*

EU countries involve:

- *Belgium*
- *Germany*
- *France*
- *Switzerland*
- *Luxembourg*
- *Nederland*

Project Name:

BE-HyFE (Belgian academic collaboration project, funded by the federal Energy Transition Fund)

Topics:

*Hydrogen value chain
Academic research*

Short description:

Hydrogen is currently experiencing a 'momentum', both politically and in the industry. Belgium has a lot of assets in the field of hydrogen: the largest hydrogen pipeline network in the world crosses our country, Belgium has a strategic position in Europe and many companies in Belgium have hydrogen technology in-house.

Additional academic fundamental research is crucial for providing solutions to the many technological and non-technological challenges posed by the role of hydrogen in our energy transition. At the different Belgian universities and knowledge institutions the expertise is highly specialized and outstanding. However, the research is fragmented and collaboration between the institutions (in the domain of hydrogen) is at this time rather limited, which is a missed opportunity.

With BE-HyFE we want to strengthen the cooperation between the Belgian hydrogen research groups and, by additional fundamental research in hydrogen, stimulate an interdisciplinary approach to create an academic hydrogen backbone for the Belgian industry. The goal of this project is to achieve a Belgian hydrogen homebase of academic knowledge and expertise by establishing a core group of 16 broadly trained and highly networked early-stage researchers (ESRs) to support the Belgian industry in finding both technological and societal solutions, guaranteeing security of supply and meeting our environmental targets.

Communalities with HYPOP:

Promote the Hydrogen value chain

There isn't European partner at the beginning of the project but one goal is to have a better international visibility with this project. Indeed, thanks to this national project, all hydrogen research is better structured and it is easier to collaborate with foreign countries.

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Project Name:

e-WallonHy (S3 Walloon project)

Topics:

*Hydrogen value chain
Coordinate the research*

*Promote the research to an industrial pilot
Hydrogen Valleys*

Short description:

e-WallonHY aims to develop a green hydrogen economy in Wallonia, including the different components of the value chain, from the production of green hydrogen (power-to-H₂), to storage and transport and its use for the most promising applications for this high purity hydrogen, namely mobility (H₂-to-Mobility) and specific industrial processes (H₂-to-Industry).

Green hydrogen is the basis of a new economic and environmental paradigm, based on local production and consumption but also on major exchanges linked to water resources and renewable energies.

Hydrogen is becoming one of the major energy vectors and will enable local and strategic energy storage.

The influence of these low-carbon technologies on the economy will depend on technological advances and the costs linked to their implementation. To achieve this influence, reducing the cost and increasing the yield of each of the components of the value chain from production to use constitute essential challenges. The technological solutions developed to meet these challenges will be designed with a minimal or even negative environmental footprint. The sizing of flexible solutions that respond specifically to the targeted decentralized applications is also a factor to consider.

The action plan includes the development of a “Made in WallonHY” label for the decentralized production of green hydrogen and its local use. Alongside large production units, increasing small production capacities linked to targeted applications also constitutes a means of reducing investment costs on each project as well as facilitating and accelerating the deployment of hydrogen on the territory, in order to achieve the ambitious objectives set by Europe, Belgium and Wallonia.

The proposed action plan aims to respond to these challenges by relying on current state-of-the-art obstacles for each technology. The science of materials and processes, in which Wallonia stands out, is one of the key areas for providing the expected innovative responses. The multidisciplinary nature of the consortium is essential to implement the action plan across the entire chain of production, transport, storage and use of hydrogen and across the entire TRL scale for integration of needs and technologies.

The deployment of the strategy will be monitored by a steering committee with representatives of research partners, industrial developers and the public sector. The steering committee will lead the action plan with a view to proposing concrete projects in which partners can participate according to their areas of activity and thus integrate all forces to reach critical masses of actors and resources.

Thanks to the actors and the convergence of the actors on an action plan, the project will become a reflection of the ecosystem and the value chain of green hydrogen which has become a major energy vector. The animation of e-WallonHy will allow the creation of transversal projects in the themes with actors to guarantee leverage effects in terms of financing and economic growth in this sector of activity.

One goal of e-WallonHy is to develop and coordinate a Hydrogen Valley in Wallonia.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
Hydrogen Valleys*

There isn't European partner for this regional project but one activity is to promote the Walloon region to international events.

2.1.8 BH2C

Project Name:

ePlus Ecosystem (Grant agreement ID: 644210, 11 December 2014)

Topics:

*Ecosystems
Industrial economy
Global business*

Short description:

The ePlus ecosystem project will develop and deploy an online and onsite environment, building on and interconnecting existing ecosystems, hubs and initiatives, in order to setup a runway for web entrepreneurs to start and scaleup a business in Europe and grow internationally. This European ecosystem will help web-entrepreneurs to develop and scale up their ideas and businesses, from a business international validation phase, to internationalization, access to finance and to business growth, thus complementing the service offer currently made available at local ecosystems level. The ePlus project will meet the objectives stated in the workprogramme in terms of accelerating web entrepreneurship in Europe, and offer a unique new platform that answers to the need for new services expressed in the Startup Manifesto. It will provide the nurturing to help web-entrepreneurs go global, through a unique combination of talents, tools and services of an European scale in all key elements required to create great companies: team, concept, technology, and capital. This will be done through the following elements:

- Putting in motion a true pan-european web-entrepreneurship ecosystem by setting up the initial backbone made of the interconnection between the booming regional ecosystems of Lisbon, Nice and Baden-Württemberg, combining and intertwining current services and opportunities and making room for more local ecosystems to join in;*
- Untap on Europe's unique mass of + 50,000 skilled and mobile researchers generated by institutions such as the Marie Curie Actions in order to reinforce the web-entrepreneurs teams' skills and technology grasp;*
- Guide web-entrepreneurs into global business concepts through a European mentoring scheme, building on the best regional and national programmes available;*

- Facilitate access to some of the best services from the best service providers in Europe to promote web-entrepreneurs growth;
- Ensure access to capital either in early stage or crowdfunding form.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Increase Eco green industry economy
Access to HE industrial project and founding
Science and Education for Smart Growth
Energy storage
Explore news energy technologies*

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Project Name:

HITMOBIL (2024)

Topics:

*Sustainable development
Integrated Energy Systems
New green technologies centers of excellence*

Short description:

Funded through the Operational Programme "Science and Education for Smart Growth" 2014-2020 and the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF), the station is a testament to Bulgaria's commitment to sustainable development. Situated within the "Integrated Energy Systems" field laboratory of the Competence Centre in Sofia, the station signifies the inception of hydrogen electric mobility in the country.

With an investment exceeding BGN 20 million (equivalent to EUR 10 million), the Competence Centre has established six state-of-the-art laboratories. Among these, four are dedicated to industrial scientific research, while two serve as hubs for experimental development, equipped with facilities for field tests and demonstrations.

The ERDF has invested over BGN 400 million (EUR 200 million) under the Operational Programme "Science and Education for Intelligent Growth" 2014-2020. This funding facilitated the establishment of six centers of excellence and ten centers of competence, which will continue to be supported under the 21-27 programming period under the Programme for Research, Innovation, and Digitalization for Smart Transformation.

The inauguration ceremony was attended by Academic Julian Revalski, Chairman of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Professor Georgi Angelov, Deputy Minister of Innovation and Growth, and Dimitar Nedyalkov, Deputy Minister of Transport and Communications.

At its core, the "HITMOBIL" project aims to construct a comprehensive national and regional infrastructure conducive to the development, testing, optimization, and industrial integration

of modern mobility and energy storage systems. Partnering with seven institutes of BAS, Neofit Rilski University of Applied Sciences, and the Association "BG H2 Society," the project epitomizes collaborative innovation towards a greener, more sustainable future.

Stara Zagora is a strategic logistic centre in Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula. It is also host to one of the biggest power production complexes in Europe (Maritsa East). This makes it the perfect location to showcase the versatility and potential of green hydrogen as means to improve air quality in the city, reduce CO2 emissions for energy production and mobility applications, and generate economic welfare.

The demonstration of clean, safe, and sustainable hydrogen technology applications will improve public perception of hydrogen ecosystems, and kick start a hydrogen-based economy not only in the region but across the country.

ZAHYR will install and demonstrate two electrolyzers with a combined installed power of 5MW, to be run on green electricity produced in a new 20MW PV plant. The hydrogen produced will be used in various transport and energy applications. These include the installation of two Hydrogen Refuelling Stations to service a fleet of 10 city buses, 2 heavy transport trucks and 2 light-duty vehicles.

A bi-fuel gas turbine will be installed in which blending limits between hydrogen and natural gas will be tested. A 1MW fuel cell at Stara Zagora will provide the municipality's public night lighting, showcasing how this municipality can become net zero emission. Finally, a broad training and education program will be set up resulting in a master's degree.

An intense replicability activity will be carried out based on the organization of the Hydrogen Valley Development Group.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Promote the Hydrogen value chain
Building regional hydrogen strategies
Regional policy improvements
Generation, storage and consumption of clean energy*

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Project Name:

Bulgaria Hydrogen Valley (activities on going)

Topics:

Creation of Hydrogen Valley in Bulgaria municipalities

Short description:

Creation of hydrogen valleys in various municipalities in Bulgaria in order to create green centers as part of the decarbonization process.

Municipality involved: Chelopech, Belovo, Topolovgrad, Asenovgrad

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Green economy
Sustainability
Decarbonization program
Green and circular economy*

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Project Name:

Zagora Sustainable Hydrogen Region (ref. n°101111903, 1 Jan 2024 - 31 Dec 2028)

Topics:

*Green power production
Carbon zero emission*

Short description:

Stara Zagora is a strategic logistic centre in Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula. It is also host to one of the biggest power production complexes in Europe (Maritsa East).

This makes it the perfect location to showcase the versatility and potential of green hydrogen as means to improve air quality in the city, reduce CO2 emissions for energy production and mobility applications, and generate economic welfare.

The demonstration of clean, safe, and sustainable hydrogen technology applications will improve public perception of hydrogen ecosystems, and kick start a hydrogen-based economy not only in the region but across the country.

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A 1MW fuel cell at Stara Zagora will provide the municipality's public night lighting, showcasing how this municipality can become net zero emission.

Finally, a broad training and education program will be set up resulting in a master's degree. An intense replicability activity will be carried out based on the organization of the Hydrogen Valley Development Group.

Communalities with HYPOP:

*Transport and energy applications
Reduce CO2 emissions
Green energy production*

2.2 Advisory Board member network

The **Advisory Board's members** represent an important opportunity to improve networking and to create synergy. Members are experts on the field of hydrogen, energy or on the social awareness activities; they are involved in several projects that might be included in the activities of HYPOP. At M12, the board has been finalised and composed of 7 members (Table 1).

Table 1 Advisory Board members

Organisation	Country	Referent
CEA Liten (Grenoble)	France	Julie Mougín
FHa - Aragon Hydrogen Foundation	Spain	Maria Luisa Martínez Orduna
H2IT Italian Hydrogen Association	Italy	Cristina Maggi
NTU Energy Research Institute @NTU ("ERI@N") ERIAN. Energy Research Institute at NTU (Nanyang Technological University)*	Singapore	Prof. CHAN Siew Hwa
Politecnico di Torino	Italy	Massimo Santarelli
RINA	Italy	Alessandra Cuneo
Università di Torino	Italy	Alessandro Sciallo

Two specific sections will be created on the project's website to give visibility to both AB members and hydrogen projects' met during this first year. This represents a first action to boost the HYPOP's community and to engage this latter into the project's activities.

A list of hydrogen related projects suggested by the AB members – or involving them directly - have been also identified (some of them have been already mentioned in the previous chapter):

- **HYDRA**- HYDrogen economy benefits and Risks tools development and policies implementation to mitigate possible climAte impacts.
<https://www.hydraproject.eu/>
- **H2SHIFT** - services for hydrogen innovation facilitation and testing
- **Unite.Energy** - Unite! Doctoral Network in Energy Storage.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101119805>
- **ComSOS** - Commercial-scale SOFC systems.
<https://www.comsos.eu/>
- **NewSOC** – Next Generation Solid Oxide Fuel Cell and Electrolysis Technology
<https://www.newsoc.eu/the-project>
- **AMPS** – Automated mass production of Solid Oxide Cells (SOC) stacks

- <https://www.amps-project.eu/>
- **HyP3D** – Hydrogen Production in pressurized 3D-printed Solid Oxide Electrolysis Stacks
<https://hyp3d.eu/>
- **CRAVE-H2** - hydrogen valley in the island of Crete incorporating energy storage applications, aggregation activities to the grid and green mobility applications.
<https://www.crave-h2.eu/>
- **IMAGHyNE** - investment to maximise the ambition for green hydrogen in Europe
<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/org-details/897474362/project/101137586/program/43108390/details>
- **HyAcademy.EU** – the European Hydrogen Academy
<https://www.hyacademy.eu/>
- **ELECTROLIFE** - Enhance knowledge on comprehensive electrolysers degradation technologies towards industrialization
<https://electrolife-project.eu/>
- **GreenSkills4H2** – development of skilled workforce in Europe for the hydrogen economy.
<https://greenskillsforhydrogen.eu/>
- **HySET (MSc Erasmus)** – Hydrogen Systems and Enabling Technologies
<https://hysetmaster.polito.it/>
- **ECOLEFINS** – Nano-Engineered Co-Ionic Ceramic Reactors for CO₂/H₂= electro-conversion to light Olefins
<https://ecolefinsproject.eu/>
- **H2iseO Hydrogen Valley** - Italian hydrogen-based industrial value chain for a sustainable mobility system in Val Camonica
https://www.fnmgroup.it/h2iseo_hydrogen_valley_en/?lang=en
- **TH2ICINO** - Towards H₂hydrogen Integrated eEconomies In NORthern Italy), hydrogen valley
<https://th2icino.eu/>
- **NAHV - NORD ADRIATIC HYDROGEN VALLEY**
<https://www.nahv.eu/>
- **HRS BOLZANO (North of Italy)**
<https://www.h2-suedtirol.com/it/il-centro-idrogeno-di-bolzano#:~:text=L'idrogeno%20compresso%20e%20stoccato,o%20carri%20trailer%20con%20autocisterne.>

First meetings with AB/projects have been organised or are under organisation. Main objective is to report main first year project's findings and to understand opportunities of synergy, stakeholder or public engagement activities. To mention as example, the H2IT - Italian Hydrogen Association, has already expressed interest in organising common events with stakeholders, but also with citizens to boost the hydrogen awareness and to support Italian projects in their deployment (e.g. hydrogen valleys development).

2.3 Networking with other key initiatives

Other networking opportunities are offered by the **Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory** and by the **EU Clean Hydrogen Mission** (Subtask 5.4.2, 5.4.3 on the GA).

A first meeting was held in November with a representative of the **Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory** in order to establish a continuous dialogue with them and to align projects' results and activities with the Observatory's needs and expectations. During the meeting, it was clear that HYPOP project focuses on a specific topic not tackled by the platform. Indeed, this latter mainly refers to hydrogen strategies in EU countries, regulation and legislation, technical aspects or ongoing projects.

HYPOP Consortium decided then to put its efforts to engage contact with the **Knowledge Hub**, that might represent a better opportunity. Hydrogen public opinion and acceptance findings within HYPOP represent interesting results and knowledge to support the hydrogen economy and its deployment. HYPOP already contributed with some information based on the first 6 project's months thanks to the data collection exercise conducted by the Clean Hydrogen JU in February 2024. More findings are now available after one year of project, it is worthing to be shared.

Thanks to the results from WP1, WP2 finalised at the present project's stage (M12), HYPOP Consortium will also move forward to contact the **Mission Innovation international platform**. It represents an important occasion to engage projects and collaborations at international levels. Possible synergies will be explored.

3 Conclusion

This document describes the synergies of the HYPOP project with other projects (EU, national, regional, etc.) which deal with green economy issues both from the point of view of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies and similar technologies which in any case pertain to the achievement of the "carbon free" objective in the next decades. Public opinion and stakeholder engagement initiatives have also been included.

With each above project a possible collaboration and synergy can be developed with HYPOP, in terms of specific activities of stakeholder and public engagement in order to support the hydrogen acceptance and trust process.

Analysing the EU projects reported in this document, the HYPOP's Partners can increase and optimized the specific expected targets (KPI, milestone, studies, dissemination, etc.).

The different approaches and methodologies of the projects, allows a multidisciplinary and multipurpose vision related to hydrogen technologies. Considering also the target of the citizens awareness and acceptance of these innovative technologies in terms of development and implementation of the green and circular economy.

Possible synergies are now under considerations in order to disseminate first project's results. A networking plan is ongoing, but effective actions will be delivered during Year 2. All results will be then reported in D5.9 – Networking with other projects and initiatives Report M24.

4 References

General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2, 12/05/2023
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, 13/03/2023
- D1.1 - State-of-the-art analysis of EU-Countries H2 strategies
- D2.1 - Report on safety requirements
- D2.2 - Report on permitting requirements
- D2.3 - Report on certification requirements

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